

COMPOSITES IN COMMERCIAL AIRCRAFT A PRODUCTION COST PERSPECTIVE

Henry R. Fenbert, P.E.
Manager
Structural Composite R&D
Operations Technology
Seattle, Washington

ABSTRACT

Composites offer significant performance benefits for commercial aircraft. Increasing use of composites is deterred by the high cost of the production process from design through component manufacture to assembly.

Four aspects of this production process are addressed as the focus of cost reduction efforts:

- Design for manufacture
- Manufacturing process development
- Health safety and environment
- Use of statistical methods

INTRODUCTION

This view of composites from a production cost perspective is the result of 27 years experience with the Boeing Commercial Airplane Company, developing manufacturing processes for composites structures on the models 727, 737, 747, 757, 767, 777, B2, A6 and V-22, within Boeing and with U.S. and foreign subcontractors. These have been years of rapid growth in the commercial jet aircraft industry. In 1965 the world market was 10 billion dollars, and in 1992 it was 30 billion dollars, both figures are in 1992 dollars. This growth has been enabled by a continual reduction in cost to the passenger as reflected in seat-mile costs.

Today, because of the world wide recession, short term growth expectations are less optimistic, but in the longer term signs point to continued rapid growth in demand for aircraft. Boeing currently has over 1300 unfilled orders in its backlog and Boeing and Airbus agree that flights by commercial airliners will increase 3-1/2 times by the year 2010.¹ Factors in this expected growth are the emergence of Asian markets, continued expansion of the U.S., European, and Japanese economies, and, most importantly, the reentry of a large part of the world into a global economy driven by trade and competition. The powerful market economy nations are hurrying to help develop and serve the potential industrial and consumer markets of eastern Europe and China. Additionally, with the two major powers no longer competing ruinously for world dominance with military might, their

energies can now be more actively directed to economic competition. One look at Japan and the European community, particularly Germany, and you see the advantage to be gained by concentrating on economic growth unburdened by the need for military might. These positive factors will continue to drive expansion of commercial aircraft product.

The increased use of composites, particularly epoxy-based glass, aramid, and carbon fiber materials, has paralleled the growth in commercial aircraft production, advancing from glass to high modulus fibers and increasing in weight percentage on successive models, culminating in the 777, a 390 seat jetliner, scheduled for service in 1995. The 777 carbon fiber/epoxy applications include floor beams and control surfaces - elevators, rudders, flaps, spoilers - which continue the design and manufacturing technology established on the models 757 and 767. The major composites advancement on the 777 is the application of carbon fiber/epoxy technology to the primary structure empennage - vertical and horizontal stabilizers. This increase has been driven by performance. Use of composites in the tail structures, as well as secondary structures, yield a weight reduction of 20-30% on a per component basis compared with aluminum structure. Added to this usage is the durability of composite components which has been excellent.

For the future, the increasing application of composites can potentially progress toward an "all-composite" high speed civil transport.

There is a significant deterrent, however. The high production costs of composites, passed on to the airlines, are cutting into profits already pressured by competition and deregulation, making it difficult to justify the considerable performance advantages of composites. What has occurred should not be too surprising, since an expanding market, performance orientation, increasing and volatile energy costs and military emphasis, in combination, do not drive costs down. In the aircraft industry also, design conservatism tends to add to production costs.

That is not to say that composites are inherently not cost effective. There are no insurmountable barriers to producing composites at costs which, coupled with their performance benefits, can result in overall cost savings to airlines and their customers. Potentially, reduced assembly and finishing costs, less material waste, larger assemblies, predictable reductions in material costs, the effects of a maturing technology (recalling that aluminum technology is already more than 60 years old), all can be expected to reduce costs. However, this expectation of reduced cost was not realized during the growth period of the 70s and 80s. Composites manufacturing costs remain significantly higher than those of the traditional aluminum alloys.

To provide an overall cost advantage to airlines, composites production costs need to be competitive with those of aluminum. The performance advantages of composites can be measured against their costs. Using weight as a principal performance characteristic, the financial benefit of weight reduction, which corresponds to the acceptable cost of such weight reduction, can be derived using fuel cost, interest rates and other factors. The generally accepted figures are \$100-\$300/lb of weight saved. One ambitious researcher with admirable initiative puts the cost at \$272/lb in 1992.² Current practice results in cost premiums well above this "hurdle rate." Military aircraft "hurdle rates", incidentally, are in the \$1000-\$2000/lb range based as they are on the higher value of speed. The "hurdle rate" for composite substitution for aluminum can change and composite materials and design advances will provide even greater weight reduction benefits. However, it is unlikely that composites use will continue to increase unless production cost reduction of composites structures is realized. Material suppliers, and fabrication equipment developers have a part to play in this production, but in my judgement, they must be led by the component producers who are focused on customer needs (airlines, passengers) as represented to them by aircraft assemblers. The component fabrication process for composites aircraft structure is considered to be the process from design to, but not including, assembly.

There are four aspects of this fabrication process which need to be focused on cost reduction. Those aspects are:

- Design for manufacture
- Manufacturing process development
- Health, safety and environment
- Use of statistical methods

THE DESIGN PROCESS

The lack of focus on manufacturing of the traditional aircraft design process has affected all manufacturers. The requirements of manufacturing need more emphasis in design development, material development, the design process itself, design changes, tolerance requirements, and process limits. All of these areas have generally been the responsibility of the design community. The task of translating these requirements into hardware is the province of the manufacturing community. This division of responsibility is well understood. What is not well understood, in practice at any rate, is the interaction between the two responsibilities. Large companies such as Boeing have taken significant steps to emphasize the interaction and de-emphasizing the division. For the 777, Boeing has integrated responsibilities in a design/build process, sometimes referred to as concurrent engineering. Design/build teams, comprised of both design and manufacturing specialists have as their objectives timely design release, minimal design changes, designs compatible with manufacturing processes, and optimal cost/performance trade-offs, all aimed at lower manufacturing costs. Because of the high subcontractual level for composite parts, Boeing has taken the further step to include subcontractor design and manufacturing personnel in these design/build teams. For the "composites showcase" components on the 777 - the primary structure empennage, the result of this design/build team process in a sophisticated design, 20% lighter than a comparable aluminum structure, fabricated with high automation content processes.

Skin Structure

The vertical and horizontal stabilizer structural boxes are faced with skins laid up by automated tape laying machines, stiffened by I-sections which in turn are fabricated by an automated tape layup, warm vacuum forming and autoclave curing process.

Spar Structure

The U-section forward and aft spars are designed for simplified layup, but, for the present, have little automation content in their processing.

Ribs

The 777 honeycomb ribs are fabricated with a hand assist lamination process (HAL) developed to blend mechanization with the hand layup process currently required for complex shapes.

Tooling

The layup and autoclave curing tool material is exclusively Invar, matching carbon fiber/epoxy coefficient of thermal expansion while providing the durability typical of metals.

Inspection

As is typical of composites structure, components are 100% ultra-sonic inspected. Two 777 innovations are continuous through-transmission ultrasonic inspection of precured stringer sections and one side pulse-echo inspection of stiffened skins.

Assembly

Close attention to detail dimensions and use of matched coefficient of thermal expansion tooling help minimize part variability. Remaining mismatch is accommodated by the use of moldable plastic shims. The ideal of shimless assembly has not yet been realized.

The preproduction success measures are positive, but the effect of these design/build teams on production costs will be closely watched and compared with previous models.

The design/build process can have an unintended consequence in limiting the amount of innovation. In the traditional system, engineering proposes an innovative design with little or no understanding of its impact on manufacturing. After the design is transferred "over the wall", manufacturing has to do whatever is necessary to produce the design. Through this sequence of activities this old, flawed system may have, at times, acted to spur technological innovation in manufacturing. In the new design/build, concurrent engineering system, a design which does not fit within the existing manufacturing technology can be vetoed by the manufacturing representatives on the team. This raises the question of whether the design/build team structure provides sufficient incentive to develop new manufacturing technology, which the old system may have (at times) promoted. An engineering representative on a critical component design/build team for an unnamed airplane stated that the designs for this component that were driven by the manufacturing representatives were usually overweight and believed that it was the manufacturing input that forced this design/build team to select heavier options.³

The design/build process will create a tighter linkage between the product design and the manufacturing processes. However, without an up-front investment in new process technology, such a product development system may slow future innovation in manufacturing processes.

PROCESS DEVELOPMENT

A number of processing techniques not yet widely applied can, with accelerated development, have a positive impact (reduction) on the cost of composites manufacturing.

Fiberplacement, pioneered by Boeing and Hercules in separate developments in the United States combines the continuous process aspects of filament winding and the complex shape capability of tape laying and can be applied to very large sections such as engine cowls and wing spars. It can be thought of as laying thin tape strand gangs on a rotating mandrel tool. The process differs from filament winding in that a mandrel-contacting head eliminates the need for a continuous strand of tape or tow. This feature allows the drop-off and pickup of strands, changing the density of strands without discontinuing processing. Their narrow width allows for turning of strands in very small radii. Thus, this innovative technology offers design flexibility, as well as a wider design envelope for application of a one-step automated process.

For smaller parts, currently laid up by hand, two technologies offer great promise. Resin transfer molding utilizes woven, knit or braided preformed dry fiber structure placed in a mold and infused with thermoset resin and non-autoclave heat cured. The advantages of this process, currently used with non-woven fibers in the auto industry - the Chrysler Viper is an example, are freedom from human contact, accommodation complexity at low cost and the promise of a one-step, finished part process.

Another technology that offers promise is based on the use of high performance thermoplastic materials whose performance rivals or betters that of epoxies, particularly in damage resistance, and repairability. These materials, for example PEEK and PEKK, combined with carbon fiber, allow for fabrication techniques similar to those of metals which can be formed quickly with the application of pressure and heat. These materials start with the production of flat stock blanks with required finish part fiber orientations. Blanks can then be formed in matched die presses or between diaphragms. Process difficulties involve high processing temperatures, ≈ 700 °F, and controlled cooling rates to balance crystallinity for solvent resistance and amorphous structure for damage resistance.

The Boeing Company is actively pursuing these technologies, aiming at application on both current and future models.

Collaboration

Just as fabricators of composite components face a serious cost dilemma in application of composites - that the performance advantages may be outweighed by the cost of design and fabrication; they face a similar dilemma in that the development of processes and equipment to reduce costs may be too expensive and not justifiable by the resultant production cost savings. To reduce these development costs, composites components manufacturers, Boeing as an example, are attempting to leverage their development investment by collaborative efforts with universities, private and government labs, consortia, and other companies.

Boeing has concentrated on universities to leverage composites manufacturing process development. Examples are: the University of Washington Polymer Composites Laboratory, a sponsor of world-wide seminars and colloquia, which last year held a colloquium on thermal analysis in Madrid in cooperation with the Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas and Massachusetts Institute of Technology's Composites Polymer Processing Program; Iowa State University, concentrating on NDI methods particularly for composites; Stanford University; University of Delaware; Clemson University, and Michigan State University also have very active composites manufacturing process programs. The advantages of such collaborative efforts are obvious - direction of University research toward corporate needs; and development, evaluation, and recruitment of top students.

Corporate proprietary rights may be protected in a university setting by paying for research. Collaborative efforts in consortia or one-to-one collaborative efforts for commercial development present more difficult proprietary information questions.

In the United States, a number of consortia bring together material producers, equipment manufacturers, academia, and fabricators of composites structures are advancing the development of manufacturing methods. Technical societies, such as the Composites Manufacturing Association of The Society of Manufacturing Engineers, continue to be important in the sharing of process information. While very supportive of technical societies, Boeing up to now has been reluctant to enter into industry consortia.

But, in a bold move to speed the development of the Very Large Commercial Transport, Boeing has entered into an agreement with key European manufacturers. From a Boeing composites technology viewpoint, this is a "blessed event" since two of these firms, DASA and CASA, are producing composite empennage structure with attractive design and manufacturing innovation.

OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT

The Boeing Company deals with the effects of processes on worker health and the environment under an umbrella designation of SHEA - Safety Health and Environmental

Affairs. This is logical for a number of reasons: 1) the near-environment for a process which the worker occupies is not different in kind from the larger environment affected by the process; 2) both are subject to local, state, national, and, eventually, international regulations which are best dealt with centrally; and 3) the cost of safety, health and environmental efforts are handled separately to, among other things, insulate these efforts from the usual "return on investment" requirements.

However, it is right and proper to consider the cost of negative effects of specific processes on worker health and the environment as a part of the total cost of these processes. Currently, companies such as Boeing associate the cost of guards, fume hoods, and other traditional safety devices with specific processes, but do not usually associate the costs of health problems such as dermatitis or repetitive motion syndrome, material disposal, cleanup costs, regulatory compliance administration costs and fines and penalties with specific processes. In industry's drive to control cost, the association of specific costs with specific processes will become more and more common practice. As this happens, composites production is especially vulnerable to scrutiny, censure and rising costs.

In composites fabrication, two areas are key to employee health and safety. First, exposure to uncured thermoset resins, mainly absorption and inhalation, and, to a lesser extent, ingestion is potentially dangerous. It is in fact a chemical handling process. Current modified epoxy materials are relatively benign, but, even so, minor changes in modified epoxy material formulations can cause worker discomfort and have significant affect on production costs. In addition, use of moderately elevated temperature to enhance manufacturing properties also enhances the chance of toxin inhalation. Worker health risk is a deterrent to development of new materials which have the potential, not only of increased structural properties, but also of increased negative affects on worker health. Secondly, the motions required to lay down, smooth and shape composite prepregs manually can easily lead to repetitive motion syndrome. These problems can be mitigated by controlling contact with protective clothing and isolation techniques and by using ergonomically designed work stations. These solutions are expensive, worker-acceptance-dependent, and need constant updating.

Boeing has made some progress toward resolution of worker contact and repetitive motion syndrome with its HAL technology which uses numerically controlled optical devices instead of cumbersome tools to indicate the placement of plies and vacuum, heat and pressure to perform some aspects of forming of composite materials. Attempts to completely automate these operations and eliminate human intervention have been unsuccessful. More effective solutions will be the use of thermoplastic technology and resin transfer molding. Thermoplastics, having no reactive materials, are less potentially dangerous and their use eliminates hand forming. Resin transfer molding eliminates manual contact, and, also, since it is a net process, eliminates the need to create trimming dust.

Additionally, resin transfer molding and fiberplacement, which have high material utilization, also factors have a positive affect on the most pressing environmental problem associated with composites - disposal and/or recycling of waste composite materials. The purchase cost of those materials, regardless of environmental effects of disposal is already driving industry to reduce waste by use of NC cutting and nesting net parts and continuous processes.

Recycling of composites is an especially thorny problem since purity of feed materials is a key to recycling processes. In composites manufacture each component must be considered a contaminant of the other components. Added to this is the fact that even the resinous components of thermoset composites are in fact mixtures. It is obvious that the individual or company that develops a recycling method other than burial or burning will have an eager, ready-made market for this technology.

STATISTICS IN PROCESSING

The increased use of statistics in all phases of composites processing is the least glamorous yet, potentially, the most immediately cost-effective change on the horizon for composites manufacturers.

In the design phase the use of statistics can help ensure matching tolerances with real process limits, thus reducing rejections generated by attempts to meet unrealistic requirements. In process development, sophisticated experimental design techniques will reduce the cost of developing realistic process limits. During the concurrent engineering test fabrication/process development phase, design of experiment techniques should be rigorously applied to assure understanding of process limits while keeping cost and flow times low.

On the 777, particular attention was paid to the affects of component variation on assembly. The data base developed will form the basis of statistically driven continuous improvement efforts to reduce variation and thus assembly costs. Statistical techniques will help focus on material variations, dimensional variations due to process-induced imbalance, and poorly matched detail tooling which lead to planned (shimming) and unplanned (rework) assembly costs.

The use of statistics is currently improving the quality of components fabricated within The Boeing Company, as well as material vendors and component and subassembly suppliers. ISO 9000 and the Boeing equivalent D-9000 will have the effect of reducing the number of subcontractors to a minimum of highly qualified, quality suppliers who can act as real partners in the development and production of composite components, using statistical techniques pivotal in assuring the quality, accuracy, and usability of these components. Statistical process control means can also reduce the inspection requirements for composites which are traditionally inspected at the 100% end product level.

SUMMARY

Composites continue to offer great performance advantages to commercial aircraft products. There will be increasing emphasis on costs as military uses become less and less important compared to commercial uses.

The cost reductions predicted for composites manufacture in the 70s and 80s have not materialized thus far in the 90s, and continued high costs will inhibit the continued growth of composites used on commercial aircraft.

With a continued need for the performance benefits of composites concentration on cost reduction through design/build teams, collaborative development efforts, application of automation, attention to health and environmental aspects, and increased use of statistical methods will be necessary to realize these benefits.

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